

Definitions of a Software Smell

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Abstract

Many authors have defined smells from their perspective. This document attempts to provide a consolidated list of such definitions.

1. Definitions

1. Smells are certain structures in the code that suggest (sometimes they scream for) the possibility of refactoring [5].
2. Code smells are a metaphor to describe patterns that are generally associated with bad design and bad programming practices [19].
3. Code smells are indicators or symptoms of the possible presence of design smells [12].
4. Code smells are implementation structures that negatively affect system lifecycle properties, such as understandability, testability, extensibility, and reusability; that is, code smells ultimately result in maintainability problems [6].
5. A “bad smell” describes a situation where there are hints that suggest there can be a design problem [13].
6. We define design defects as solutions to recurring problems that generate negative consequences on the quality of object-oriented systems [11].
7. Antipatterns are “poor” solutions to recurring implementation and design problems that impede the maintenance and evolution of programs [9].
8. Anti-patterns are bad solutions to recurring design problems [4].
9. An anti-pattern is a commonly occurring solution to a recurring problem that will typically negatively impact code quality. Code smells are

considered to be symptoms of anti-patterns and occur at source code level [14].

10. Antipatterns are defined as patterns that appear obvious but are ineffective or far from optimal in practice, representing worst practices about how to structure and design an ontology [15].
11. Anti-patterns are “poor” solutions to recurring design and implementation problems [10].
12. Developers often introduce bad solutions, anti-patterns, to recurring design problems in their systems and these anti-patterns lead to negative effects on code quality [7].
13. Linguistic antipatterns in software systems are recurring poor practices in the naming, documentation, and choice of identifiers in the implementation of an entity, thus possibly impairing program understanding [1].
14. Design smells are structures in the design that indicate violation of fundamental design principles and negatively impact design quality [18].
15. Code smells are indicators of deeper design problems that may cause difficulties in the evolution of a software system [20].
16. Performance Antipatterns define bad practices that induce performance problems, and their solutions [2].
17. Antipatterns are typically a commonly used set of design and coding constructs which might appear intuitive initially, but eventually may be detrimental to one or more aspects of the system [17].
18. Bad design practices at the code level are known as bad smells in the literature [8].
19. Code smells — microstructures in the program — have been used to reveal surface indications of a design problem [3].
20. Configuration smells are the characteristics of a configuration program or script that violate the recommended best practices and potentially affect the programs quality in a negative way [16].

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